

SUPPORTING INFORMATION:

Quantum chemical roots of machine-learning molecular similarity descriptors

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1 Coulomb Matrix and Coulomb List

1.1 Effects of Scaling on $\mathcal{F}_n^{(J)}$ and $\mathcal{F}_e^{(J)}$

The nuclear repulsion feature, $\mathcal{F}_n^{(J)}$, which contains a sum over the nuclei I , can be scaled by a constant Z_J , the nuclear charge number Z_J of the nucleus of the feature in question. Conceptually, the plots do not reveal more hidden structure. Nevertheless, for the sake of completeness we show a scaled version of Figure 2 from the main article here as SI Figure 1, where both $\mathcal{F}_n^{(J)}$ and $\mathcal{F}_e^{(J)}$ are shown unscaled (in the left column) and scaled (in the right column). Naturally, the shapes of the traces do not change but note the change of the y-axes. Furthermore, we show the correlation plot between scaled $\mathcal{F}_n^{(J)}$ and scaled $\mathcal{F}_e^{(J)}$ as SI Figure 2, which relates to Figure 3 in the main article. Due to the scaled axes, it is possible to represent the entire data range without loss of clarity on the same axes magnitudes.

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Figure 1: For reaction 1 of Figure 1 in the main article: (a) the external potential features, $\mathcal{F}_e^{(J)}$, (b) the external potential features scaled by Z_J , (c) the nuclear repulsion features, $\mathcal{F}_n^{(J)}$, and (d) the nuclear repulsion features scaled by Z_J , are shown in Hartree (E_h). (TS denoted blue, reactant and product ans green and red, respectively.) The 4 subplots are sorted by element and the ordering in each subplot according to increasing value of the TS structure feature. The left column corresponds to the Figure 2 in the main article.

Figure 2: External potential features, $\mathcal{F}_e^{(J)}$, and nuclear repulsion features, $\mathcal{F}_n^{(J)}$, each scaled by the respective nuclear charge, Z_J , to bring them to a similar order of magnitude. The correlation within any element is large over all elements and over the course of the reaction from reactant to TS structure to product, as observed in the unscaled version of Figure 3 in the main article.

2 SOED: Technical Derivations

As we have seen in the main article, the analytic derivation of SOED involves polynomial prefactors (originating from $l \leq 1$ -type basis functions) that makes a fully analytical evaluation difficult. In the main article, we therefore adopted approximations that allowed us to exploit standard SOAP protocol (lobe functions). Here, we provide additional information on these approximations as well as a sketch of the analytical derivation that avoids these approximations.

2.1 Lobe functions to approximate p -functions

One complication — apart from the fact that LCAO basis set contractions with fixed expansion coefficients require an inheritance pattern of coefficients when combined with the molecular orbital coefficients — of the SOED derivation originates from the two-center integrals over functions of high orbital angular momentum quantum number (p -functions in our case, but this applies also to d -functions and so forth). Note that this type of functions is not present in SOAP as the molecular scaffold density is constructed from single s -functions without any product forms.

A rather old recipe is to represent these high- l functions by lobe functions, i.e., s -functions with shifted centers, which is advantageous in our case as we can then take advantage of the SOAP formalism. A p_x function, for instance, can be approximated by two (or more) s -functions. Unlike in standard SOAP, where every s -type Gaussian function has the same width parameter, in our case, the width would be a fit parameter to best approximate a p -function of the LCAO basis. A similar procedure works for d -functions, albeit it was not needed for STO-3G and the molecules studied here.

However, instead of one Gaussian per atom for SOAP, we generate Aufpunkte for s -functions that do not correspond to atomic nuclei. Moreover, the fact that LCAO basis functions and, hence, also the lobe functions enter the density in a bilinear fashion due to the squared molecular orbitals, makes the SOED calculation even more complicated than the standard SOAP evaluation. For instance, if any given atom has two s -functions and a p -function, instead of having a single s -type Gaussian at that atom’s nucleus position for SOAP, there would be 8 Aufpunkte, two superimposed at the actual nuclear position for the two different s -functions, and 6 Aufpunkte slightly shifted from the nuclear position along the coordinate axes, two for each of p_x , p_y , and p_z -function. In the electron density expression, more Aufpunkte are generated for the product function of two s -functions by virtue of the Gaussian product theorem.

In the following, we sketch how the shifted centers and parameters in the exponent of the lobe functions are determined deterministically for any given p -function in the basis set. The radial part of the p -function in one dimension is

$$f_p(N_p, \zeta_p, x) = N_p x \exp(-\zeta_p x^2) \quad (1)$$

with position variable x , normalization constant N_p set to unity w.l.o.g., and width parameter ζ_p . It will be approximated by two s -functions, a positive and a negative,

$$f_s(N_s, \zeta_s, h, x) = N_s(\exp(-\zeta_s(x-h)^2) - \exp(-\zeta_s(x+h)^2)) \quad (2)$$

where the distance h denotes the distance of the Aufpunkt of the s -function to the position of the nucleus at which the p -function is centered, N_s denotes the normalization constant, and ζ_s denotes the width of the new s -function. An overlay of the two functions can be seen in SI Figure 3 with arbitrary parameters.

Figure 3: The sum, f_s (red), of two s -functions (orange and green), approximate a p -function, f_p (blue). The parameters are set arbitrarily to $\zeta_p = 1/2$, $\zeta_s = 1/2$, $h = 1$ and both normalization constants, $N_s = N_p = 1$, i.e., they are not optimized to fit the p -function in order to demonstrate the concept.

Even though the integral $\int |f_p - f_s|^2 dx$ is analytically solvable, the minimization of it is not. We decided to avoid numerical procedures, such that all steps are analytical: We will match the features of both functions.

At the origin, $x = 0$, the slope of f_p is N_p which we set to unity above,

$$\left. \frac{d}{dx} f_p(N_p = 1, \zeta_p, x) \right|_{x=0} = e^{-\zeta_p x^2} - 2\zeta_p x^2 e^{-\zeta_p x^2} \Big|_{x=0} = 1 = N_p . \quad (3)$$

The slope of both functions should match at the origin. Since for f_p , the slope is 1, we set the slope of f_s to 1 to obtain the normalization constant, N_s ,

$$\left. \frac{d}{dx} f_s(N_s, \zeta_s, h, x) \right|_{x=0} = 2\zeta_s N_s \left((h+x)e^{-\zeta_s(h+x)^2} - (x-h)e^{-\zeta_s(x-h)^2} \right) \Big|_{x=0} \stackrel{!}{=} 1 \quad (4)$$

which yields

$$N_s = \frac{e^{\zeta_s h^2}}{4\zeta_s h} . \quad (5)$$

By setting N_s this way, it is guaranteed that f_s has the same slope at the origin as f_p .

As a second feature-matching characteristic, we search for the extrema of f_p and require those of f_s to be at the same location. By setting the derivative of f_p to 0, we obtain the extrema at $x = \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\zeta_p}}$. Now, we require f_s also to have zero slope at the extrema positions that yields a width, subject to be real and positive,

$$\left. \frac{d}{dx} f_s(N_s, \zeta_s, h, x) \right|_{x=\pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\zeta_p}}} \stackrel{!}{=} 0 \quad (6)$$

which is the same for both extrema, i.e. independent of the sign of the extrema position, yielding

$$\zeta_s = - \frac{\sqrt{\zeta_p} \log \left(\frac{\sqrt{2} - 2\sqrt{\zeta_p h}}{2\sqrt{\zeta_p h} + \sqrt{2}} \right)}{2\sqrt{2}h} \quad (7)$$

with h is constraint according to $0 < h < \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\zeta_p}}$. This new ζ_s can also be re-substituted into the N_s we found above, Eq. (5), to obtain ζ_s and N_s that describe f_s dependent on only ζ_p and h . The free parameter h has to obey the constraint above and the approximation will be best for small h . As can be seen in Figure 4, the largest error for a difference between f_p and f_s with $h = 1/2$ is generally very low.

As an example, we consider a H₂O molecule in the minimal basis STO-3G. The oxygen nucleus carries the following functions: $1s$, $2s$, $3p_x$, $3p_y$, $3p_z$, all have 3 primitives per shell. The p_z -function has a primitive exponent for the first primitive shell of $\zeta_p = 5.03315132$. To build f_s that approximates this p_z function, we employ Eq. (7) with ζ_p and $h = 0.001$ (denoting the distance of the new s -function from the origin) to get a new exponent for the s -functions, $\zeta_s = 5.03318$. The resulting ζ_s can be used with Eq. (5) to obtain a normalization constant $N_s = 49.6706$. From the set of 3 p -functions, we thus obtain 18 s -functions. In total we get 3 per s -function (two on oxygen, one each on hydrogen), which is 12, with 18 from the approximated p -function, yielding 30 functions instead of 15.

With this process of replacing all higher-order functions with s -functions, we obtain a structure that can be subjected to the same process as SOAP to obtain a SOAP-like kernel, based on density. From the point of view of molecular scaffold densities in SOAP, this appears then as a ‘new’ molecule which comprises the nuclear coordinates of the true one but contains much more ‘pseudo-atoms’.

Figure 4: The difference between f_s and f_p with the fitted parameters N_s and ζ_s with $h = 1/2$.

Instead of setting the SOAP exponents $\alpha \leftarrow \alpha_I$ as explained in main article in section 5.1, we keep them all different for each I according to the LCAO exponents, as we defined it in Eq. (34) in the main text. Furthermore, I is no longer running over all nuclei anymore as in SOAP.

2.2 Analytical derivation

2.2.1 Representing all Gaussian parts in polar coordinates, centered at the origin of the coordinate system for SOED

The Gaussians, $g_\alpha(\mathbf{r}_A)$ and $g_\beta(\mathbf{r}_B)$, can be expanded as in the SOAP procedure (see section 5.1 in the main article with a plane wave (as Eq. (15)) where we substitute the Legendre polynomial via the spherical harmonics addition theorem Eq. (17).

This yields the Gaussians

$$g_\alpha(\mathbf{r}_A) = 4\pi \exp(-\zeta_\alpha(r^2 + R_A^2)) \sum_{l^{(\alpha)} m^{(\alpha)}} i_{l^{(\alpha)}}(2\zeta_\alpha r R_A) Y_{l^{(\alpha)} m^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega) Y_{l^{(\alpha)} m^{(\alpha)}}^*(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_A}), \quad (8)$$

and

$$g_\beta(\mathbf{r}_B) = 4\pi \exp(-\zeta_\beta(r^2 + R_B^2)) \sum_{l^{(\beta)} m^{(\beta)}} i_{l^{(\beta)}}(2\zeta_\beta r R_B) Y_{l^{(\beta)} m^{(\beta)}}(\Omega) Y_{l^{(\beta)} m^{(\beta)}}^*(\Omega_{\mathbf{r}_B}), \quad (9)$$

similar to Eq. (18) with Eq. (19) in the main article.

2.2.2 Representing all polynomials in polar coordinates, centered at the origin of the coordinate system for SOED

Now, we will bring the polynomial part from Eq. (44) of the GTO function in Eq. (43) into a convenient, single-center, angle-dependent form.

As Moshinsky shows,¹ in his Eq. (46) the polynomial can be expanded as

$$\begin{aligned} f_\alpha(\mathbf{r}_A) &= |\mathbf{r}_A|^{L_\alpha} Y_{L_\alpha M_\alpha}(\Omega_{\mathbf{r}_A}) \\ &= \sum_{l_1, l_2=0}^{L_\alpha} \delta_{l_1+l_2, L_\alpha} G(l_1, l_2, L_\alpha) \\ &\quad \times \sum_{m_1, m_2} \langle l_1 l_2 m_1 m_2 | L_\alpha M_\alpha \rangle r^{l_1} Y_{l_1 m_1}(\Omega) R_A^{l_2} Y_{l_2 m_2}(\Omega_{\mathbf{r}_A}) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

with the Clebsch-Gordan coefficient $\langle l_1 l_2 m_1 m_2 | L_\alpha M_\alpha \rangle$ and the coefficient

$$G(l_1, l_2, L_\alpha) = (-1)^{l_2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi (2L_\alpha + 1)!}{(2l_1 + 1)! (2l_2 + 1)!}}. \quad (11)$$

This is now dependent on a single center at the origin of the coordinate system and not on a local frame of reference at each core, $\mathbf{r}_A$.

2.2.3 Combining the single-center Gaussians and polynomials into a GTO

Together with the Gaussian expressed in single-centered spherical coordinates, employing a composite index $ab \equiv (\alpha, \beta, \mathbf{R}_{\alpha\beta}, L_\alpha, M_\alpha, L_\beta, M_\beta)$, this yields for a single function

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi_{ab}(\mathbf{r}) &= N_{\alpha\beta} g_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r}_A) g_{\beta}(\mathbf{r}_B) f_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r}_A) f_{\beta}(\mathbf{r}_B) \\
&= 4\pi N_{\alpha} \exp(-\zeta_{\alpha}(r^2 + R_A^2)) \\
&\quad \times \sum_{l^{(\alpha)} m^{(\alpha)}} Y_{l^{(\alpha)} m^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega) Y_{l^{(\alpha)} m^{(\alpha)}}^*(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_A}) i_{l^{(\alpha)}}(2\zeta_{\alpha} r R_A) \\
&\quad \times 4\pi N_{\beta} \exp(-\zeta_{\beta}(r^2 + R_B^2)) \\
&\quad \times \sum_{l^{(\beta)} m^{(\beta)}} Y_{l^{(\beta)} m^{(\beta)}}(\Omega) Y_{l^{(\beta)} m^{(\beta)}}^*(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_B}) i_{l^{(\beta)}}(2\zeta_{\beta} r R_B) \\
&\quad \times \sum_{l_1^{(\alpha)}, l_2^{(\alpha)}}^{L_{\alpha}} \delta_{l_1^{(\alpha)} + l_2^{(\alpha)}, L_{\alpha}} G(l_1^{(\alpha)}, l_2^{(\alpha)}, L_{\alpha}) \\
&\quad \times \sum_{m_1^{(\alpha)}, m_2^{(\alpha)}} \langle l_1^{(\alpha)} l_2^{(\alpha)} m_1^{(\alpha)} m_2^{(\alpha)} | L_{\alpha} M_{\alpha} \rangle r^{l_1^{(\alpha)}} Y_{l_1^{(\alpha)} m_1^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega) R_A^{l_2^{(\alpha)}} Y_{l_2^{(\alpha)} m_2^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_A}) \\
&\quad \times \sum_{l_1^{(\beta)}, l_2^{(\beta)}}^{L_{\beta}} \delta_{l_1^{(\beta)} + l_2^{(\beta)}, L_{\beta}} G(l_1^{(\beta)}, l_2^{(\beta)}, L_{\beta}) \\
&\quad \times \sum_{m_1^{(\beta)}, m_2^{(\beta)}} \langle l_1^{(\beta)} l_2^{(\beta)} m_1^{(\beta)} m_2^{(\beta)} | L_{\beta} M_{\beta} \rangle r^{l_1^{(\beta)}} Y_{l_1^{(\beta)} m_1^{(\beta)}}(\Omega) R_B^{l_2^{(\beta)}} Y_{l_2^{(\beta)} m_2^{(\beta)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_B})
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

and with help of the fact that the Clebsch-Gordan coefficients are the expansion coefficients of a product of two spherical harmonics in terms of a single spherical harmonic,

$$Y_{l' m'}(\Omega) Y_{l'' m''}(\Omega) = \sum_{lm} H(l', l'', l) \langle l' l'' m' m'' | lm \rangle Y_{lm}(\Omega) \tag{13}$$

where

$$H(l', l'', l) = \sqrt{\frac{(2l' + 1)(2l'' + 1)}{4\pi(2l + 1)}} \langle l' l'' 00 | l0 \rangle \tag{14}$$

we can contract a few terms.

The indices where the limits are not explicitly given obey the triangle inequality,

$$\begin{aligned}
|l_1 - l| &\leq l' \leq l_1 + l \\
|l_2 - l| &\leq l'' \leq l_2 + l \\
m_1 + m_2 &= m' + m'' = M_{\alpha}
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

and $l_1 + l + l''$ and $l_2 + l + l''$ both even, otherwise H will evaluate to 0. These rules apply for both cases, denotes with a superscript (α) and (β) .

We can group the spherical harmonics with the same angular information together, namely $Y_{l^{(\alpha)}m^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega)$ and $Y_{l_1^{(\alpha)}m_1^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega)$, and $Y_{l^{(\beta)}m^{(\beta)}}(\Omega)$ and $Y_{l_1^{(\beta)}m_1^{(\beta)}}(\Omega)$, where the result of each of these pairs contains another spherical harmonic than can recursively be summarized again, as well as $Y_{l^{(\alpha)}m^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_A})$ and $Y_{l_2^{(\alpha)}m_2^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_A})$ and $Y_{l^{(\beta)}m^{(\beta)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_B})$ and $Y_{l_2^{(\beta)}m_2^{(\beta)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_B})$, all with Eqs. (13) and (14).

Hence

$$Y_{l_1^{(\alpha)}m_1^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega)Y_{l^{(\alpha)}m^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega) = \sum_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}} H(l_1^{(\alpha)}, l^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}) \langle l_1^{(\alpha)} l^{(\alpha)} m_1^{(\alpha)} m^{(\alpha)} | l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} \rangle Y_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega), \quad (16)$$

and

$$Y_{l_1^{(\beta)}m_1^{(\beta)}}(\Omega)Y_{l^{(\beta)}m^{(\beta)}}(\Omega) = \sum_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}} H(l_1^{(\beta)}, l^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}) \langle l_1^{(\beta)} l^{(\beta)} m_1^{(\beta)} m^{(\beta)} | l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} \rangle Y_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}}(\Omega), \quad (17)$$

where the resulting spherical harmonics at the very end of the two expressions above can be contracted again,

$$Y_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega)Y_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}}(\Omega) = \sum_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}} H(l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}) \langle l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} | l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} \rangle Y_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}}(\Omega). \quad (18)$$

Furthermore,

$$Y_{l_2^{(\alpha)}m_2^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_A})Y_{l^{(\alpha)}m^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_A}) = \sum_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}} H(l_2^{(\alpha)}, l^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}) \langle l_2^{(\alpha)} l^{(\alpha)} m_2^{(\alpha)} m^{(\alpha)} | l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} \rangle Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_A}), \quad (19)$$

and

$$Y_{l_2^{(\beta)}m_2^{(\beta)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_B})Y_{l^{(\beta)}m^{(\beta)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_B}) = \sum_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}} H(l_2^{(\beta)}, l^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}) \langle l_2^{(\beta)} l^{(\beta)} m_2^{(\beta)} m^{(\beta)} | l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)} \rangle Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_B}), \quad (20)$$

which cannot be further contracted due to the different angle argument of the spherical harmonics. Now, we can rewrite Eq. (12) as follows, where we reduced the number of spherical harmonics from eight to three yet have a 22-fold sum,

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi_{ab}(\mathbf{r}) &= 16\pi^2 N_{\alpha\beta} \exp(-\zeta_\alpha(r^2 + R_A^2)) \exp(-\zeta_\beta(r^2 + R_B^2)) \\
&\times \sum_{l^{(\alpha)} m^{(\alpha)}} (-1)^{m^{(\alpha)}} \sum_{l^{(\beta)} m^{(\beta)}} (-1)^{m^{(\beta)}} i_{l^{(\alpha)}}(2\zeta_\alpha r R_A) i_{l^{(\beta)}}(2\zeta_\beta r R_B) \\
&\times \sum_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}} H(l_1^{(\alpha)}, l^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}) \langle l_1^{(\alpha)} l^{(\alpha)} m_1^{(\alpha)} m^{(\alpha)} | l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} \rangle \\
&\times \sum_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}} H(l_1^{(\beta)}, l^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}) \langle l_1^{(\beta)} l^{(\beta)} m_1^{(\beta)} m^{(\beta)} | l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} \rangle \\
&\times \sum_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}} H(l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}) \langle l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} | l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} \rangle Y_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}}(\Omega) \\
&\times \sum_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}} H(l_2^{(\alpha)}, l^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}) \langle l_2^{(\alpha)} l^{(\alpha)} m_2^{(\alpha)} - m^{(\alpha)} | l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} \rangle Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_A}) \\
&\times \sum_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}} H(l_2^{(\beta)}, l^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}) \langle l_2^{(\beta)} l^{(\beta)} m_2^{(\beta)} - m^{(\beta)} | l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)} \rangle Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_B}) \\
&\times \sum_{l_1^{(\alpha)}, l_2^{(\alpha)}}^{L_\alpha} \delta_{l_1^{(\alpha)} + l_2^{(\alpha)}, L_\alpha} G(l_1^{(\alpha)}, l_2^{(\alpha)}, L_\alpha) \\
&\times \sum_{m_1^{(\alpha)}, m_2^{(\alpha)}} \langle l_1^{(\alpha)} l_2^{(\alpha)} m_1^{(\alpha)} m_2^{(\alpha)} | L_\alpha M_\alpha \rangle r^{l_1^{(\alpha)}} R_A^{l_2^{(\alpha)}} \\
&\times \sum_{l_1^{(\beta)}, l_2^{(\beta)}}^{L_\beta} \delta_{l_1^{(\beta)} + l_2^{(\beta)}, L_\beta} G(l_1^{(\beta)}, l_2^{(\beta)}, L_\beta) \\
&\times \sum_{m_1^{(\beta)}, m_2^{(\beta)}} \langle l_1^{(\beta)} l_2^{(\beta)} m_1^{(\beta)} m_2^{(\beta)} | L_\beta M_\beta \rangle r^{l_1^{(\beta)}} R_B^{l_2^{(\beta)}} .
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

It can be shown that the multiple sums over the Clebsch-Gordan coefficients can be simplified to a product of a 6-j coefficient and a Wigner 3-j symbol.²⁻⁴ For this we need to transform all but the brown Clebsch-Gordan coefficients into Wigner 3-j symbols,

$$\langle j_1 j_2 m_1 m_2 | j_3 m_3 \rangle = (-1)^{-j_1 + j_2 - m_3} \sqrt{2j_3 + 1} \begin{pmatrix} j_1 & j_2 & j_3 \\ m_1 & m_2 & -m_3 \end{pmatrix} . \tag{22}$$

With the help of graphical methods^{2,3} we can show that the jm-symbol holds,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{n_1 n_2 n_3} (-1)^{l_1 - n_1 + l_2 - n_2 + l_3 - n_3} \times \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & j_1 & l_2 \\ n_1 & m_1 & n_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} l_2 & j_2 & l_3 \\ -n_2 & m_2 & n_3 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} l_3 & j_3 & l_1 \\ -n_3 & m_3 & -n_1 \end{pmatrix} \\
& = (-1)^{j_1 - j_2 + j_3} \left\{ \begin{matrix} j_1 & j_2 & j_3 \\ l_3 & l_1 & l_2 \end{matrix} \right\} \begin{pmatrix} j_1 & j_2 & j_3 \\ m_1 & m_2 & m_3 \end{pmatrix} \\
& \tag{23}
\end{aligned}$$

Hence in our case we get for the (α) -case (and similarly for (β)),

$$\begin{aligned}
w^{(\alpha)} & = \langle l_1^{(\alpha)} l_1^{(\alpha)} m_1^{(\alpha)} m^{(\alpha)} | l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} \rangle \langle l_2^{(\alpha)} l_2^{(\alpha)} m_2^{(\alpha)} - m^{(\alpha)} | l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} \rangle \langle l_1^{(\alpha)} l_2^{(\alpha)} m_1^{(\alpha)} m_2^{(\alpha)} | L_{\alpha} M_{\alpha} \rangle \\
& = P^{(\alpha)} \begin{pmatrix} l_1^{(\alpha)} & l^{(\alpha)} & l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} \\ m_1^{(\alpha)} & m^{(\alpha)} & -m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} l_2^{(\alpha)} & l^{(\alpha)} & l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} \\ m_2^{(\alpha)} & -m^{(\alpha)} & -m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} l_1^{(\alpha)} & l_2^{(\alpha)} & L_{\alpha} \\ m_1^{(\alpha)} & m_2^{(\alpha)} & -M_{\alpha} \end{pmatrix} \\
& \tag{24}
\end{aligned}$$

with the sign and prefactor

$$P^{(\alpha)} = (-1)^{-l_1^{(\alpha)} + l^{(\alpha)} - m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}} \sqrt{2l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} + 1} (-1)^{-l_2^{(\alpha)} + l^{(\alpha)} - m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}} \sqrt{2l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} + 1} (-1)^{-l_1^{(\alpha)} + l_2^{(\alpha)} - M_{\alpha}} \sqrt{2L_{\alpha} + 1}. \tag{25}$$

We have to bring the product into the right shape to apply the identity of Eq. (23), hence we permute the columns of the 3-j symbols. They are invariant under an even number of permutations and they yield a phase factor of $(-1)^{j_1 + j_2 + j_3}$ for an odd number of permutations. In the product of three Wigner 3-j symbols,

- in the first, we permute the second and third column, with no phase factor
- in the second, we permute first the first and the second, then the second and the third column, with phase factor $(-1)^{l_2^{(\alpha)} + l^{(\alpha)} + l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}}$,
- and in the third, we permute first the first and the second, then the second and the third column, with phase factor $(-1)^{l_1^{(\alpha)} + l_2^{(\alpha)} + L_{\alpha}}$

yielding

$$\begin{aligned}
w^{(\alpha)} & = P^{(\alpha)} (-1)^{l_2^{(\alpha)} + l^{(\alpha)} + l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}} (-1)^{l_1^{(\alpha)} + l_2^{(\alpha)} + L_{\alpha}} \\
& \times \begin{pmatrix} l_1^{(\alpha)} & l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} & l^{(\alpha)} \\ m_1^{(\alpha)} & -m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} & m^{(\alpha)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} l^{(\alpha)} & l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} & l_2^{(\alpha)} \\ -m^{(\alpha)} & -m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} & m_2^{(\alpha)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} l_2^{(\alpha)} & L_{\alpha} & l_1^{(\alpha)} \\ m_2^{(\alpha)} & -M_{\alpha} & m_1^{(\alpha)} \end{pmatrix} \\
& \tag{26}
\end{aligned}$$

where we see that the top left and right indices inside the Wigner 3-j symbols match each other.

Using that $w^{(\alpha)}$ and substitute it into Eq. (23), we get the following for (α) and similarly for (β) , using the graphical method software by Xiang:⁵

$$W^{(\alpha)} = (-1)^{L_A + l^{(\alpha)} + M_A} \times \sqrt{(2L_A + 1)(2l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} + 1)(2l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} + 1)} \left\{ \begin{array}{ccc} l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} & l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} & L_A \\ l_2^{(\alpha)} & l_1^{(\alpha)} & l^{(\alpha)} \end{array} \right\} \left(\begin{array}{ccc} l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} & l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} & L_A \\ m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} & m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} & -M_A \end{array} \right) \quad (27)$$

Hence we can reduce the 22-fold sum in Eq. (21) to a 16-fold sum, as 6 indices, m_1 , m_2 and m for (α) and (β) fall away.

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_{ab}(\mathbf{r}) &= 16\pi^2 N_{\alpha\beta} \exp(-\zeta_\alpha(r^2 + R_A^2)) \exp(-\zeta_\beta(r^2 + R_B^2)) \\ &\times \sum_{l^{(\alpha)} l^{(\beta)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}} \sum_{l_1^{(\alpha)}, l_2^{(\alpha)}=0}^{L_\alpha} \sum_{l_1^{(\beta)}, l_2^{(\beta)}=0}^{L_\beta} \\ &(-1)^{m^{(\alpha)}} (-1)^{m^{(\beta)}} i_{l^{(\alpha)}}(2\zeta_\alpha r R_A) i_{l^{(\beta)}}(2\zeta_\beta r R_B) \\ &\times H(l_1^{(\alpha)}, l^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}) H(l_1^{(\beta)}, l^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}) \\ &\times H(l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}) \langle l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} | l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} \rangle Y_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}}(\Omega) \\ &\times H(l_2^{(\alpha)}, l^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}) Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_A}) \quad (28) \\ &\times H(l_2^{(\beta)}, l^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}) Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_B}) \\ &\times \delta_{l_1^{(\alpha)} + l_2^{(\alpha)}, L_\alpha} G(l_1^{(\alpha)}, l_2^{(\alpha)}, L_\alpha) \\ &\times r^{l_1^{(\alpha)}} R_A^{l_2^{(\alpha)}} \\ &\times \delta_{l_1^{(\beta)} + l_2^{(\beta)}, L_\beta} G(l_1^{(\beta)}, l_2^{(\beta)}, L_\beta) \\ &\times r^{l_1^{(\beta)}} R_B^{l_2^{(\beta)}} \\ &\times W^{(\alpha)} W^{(\beta)} \end{aligned}$$

To make the expression more concise, we define a new coefficient,

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\alpha,\beta} &\equiv C(l_1^{(\alpha)}, l_1^{(\beta)}, l_2^{(\alpha)}, l_2^{(\beta)}, l^{(\alpha)}, l^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}, m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}, m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}, m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}, m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}, m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}, L_\alpha, L_\beta, M_\alpha, M_\beta) \\ &= \delta_{l_1^{(\alpha)} + l_2^{(\alpha)}, L_\alpha} \delta_{l_1^{(\beta)} + l_2^{(\beta)}, L_\beta} \\ &\times G(l_1^{(\alpha)}, l_2^{(\alpha)}, L_\alpha) G(l_1^{(\beta)}, l_2^{(\beta)}, L_\beta) \\ &\times H(l_1^{(\alpha)}, l^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}) H(l_1^{(\beta)}, l^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}) \\ &\times H(l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}) \langle l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} | l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} \rangle \\ &\times H(l_2^{(\alpha)}, l^{(\alpha)}, l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}) H(l_2^{(\beta)}, l^{(\beta)}, l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}) \\ &\times W^{(\alpha)} W^{(\beta)} \quad (29) \end{aligned}$$

to write the GTO as

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi_{ab}(\mathbf{r}) &= 16\pi^2 N_{\alpha\beta} \exp(-\zeta_\alpha(r^2 + R_A^2)) \exp(-\zeta_\beta(r^2 + R_B^2)) \\
&\times \sum_{l^{(\alpha)} l^{(\beta)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\beta)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}} \sum_{l_1^{(\alpha)}, l_2^{(\alpha)}=0}^{L_\alpha} \sum_{l_1^{(\beta)}, l_2^{(\beta)}=0}^{L_\beta} C_{\alpha,\beta} \\
&\times r^{l_1^{(\alpha)}} R_A^{l_2^{(\alpha)}} \\
&\times r^{l_1^{(\beta)}} R_B^{l_2^{(\beta)}} \\
&\times i_{l^{(\alpha)}}(2\zeta_\alpha r R_A) i_{l^{(\beta)}}(2\zeta_\beta r R_B) \\
&\times Y_{l_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)} m_{\mathbf{r}}^{(\alpha\beta)}}(\Omega) Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_A}) Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_B})
\end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

which is inefficient to calculate due to the 16-fold sum. Yet the terms from the various coefficients nested inside $C_{\alpha,\beta}$ can be precalculated and stored for fast evaluation.

2.2.4 Calculating the overlap

An overlap, S , of two densities, Eq. (25) in the main article, one of which is rotated with a rotation operator $\hat{R}$, is

$$S = \langle \rho_{\text{el}}(\mathbf{r}) | \hat{R} | \rho'_{\text{el}}(\mathbf{r}) \rangle = \sum_{\substack{A,B, \\ C,D}}^M \sum_{\substack{\alpha \otimes A \\ \beta \otimes B}} \sum_{\substack{\gamma \otimes C \\ \delta \otimes D}} D_{\alpha\beta} D_{\gamma\delta} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \chi_{\alpha\beta} \hat{R} \chi_{\gamma\delta} d\mathbf{r}, \tag{31}$$

where $d\mathbf{r} = dx dy dz$. This leads to an expression that includes an integral over a product of four GTOs and hence the product of four Gaussians. In order to evaluate the action of the rotation operator, we require an expression that is dependent on polar angles θ and ϕ . The SOAP procedure⁶ expands the Gaussians into spherical harmonics and Bessel functions as we did for Eq. (8). Substituting the expression for the single-center GTO, Eq. (30), into Eq. (31) results in an integral over the product of four Bessel functions, a Gaussian, and a power.

We obtain the overlap

$$\begin{aligned}
S &= \sum_{\substack{A,B, \\ C,D}}^M \sum_{\substack{\alpha \in A \\ \beta \in B}} \sum_{\substack{\gamma \in C \\ \delta \in D}} D_{\alpha\beta} D_{\gamma\delta} \\
&\times 256\pi^4 N_{\alpha\beta} N_{\gamma\delta} \\
&\times \sum_{l^{(\alpha)} l^{(\beta)}} \sum_{l_r^{(\alpha)} m_r^{(\alpha)}} \sum_{l_r^{(\beta)} m_r^{(\beta)}} \sum_{l_r^{(\alpha\beta)} m_r^{(\alpha\beta)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}} \sum_{l_1^{(\alpha)}, l_2^{(\alpha)}}^{L_\alpha} \sum_{l_1^{(\beta)}, l_2^{(\beta)}}^{L_\beta} \\
&\times \sum_{l^{(\gamma)} m^{(\gamma)}} \sum_{l^{(\delta)} m^{(\delta)}} \sum_{l_r^{(\gamma)} m_r^{(\gamma)}} \sum_{l_r^{(\delta)} m_r^{(\delta)}} \sum_{l_r^{(\gamma\delta)} m_r^{(\gamma\delta)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)}} \sum_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\delta)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\delta)}} \sum_{l_1^{(\gamma)}, l_2^{(\gamma)}}^{L_\gamma} \sum_{l_1^{(\delta)}, l_2^{(\delta)}}^{L_\delta} \\
&\times \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} C_{\alpha,\beta} \exp(-\zeta_\alpha(r^2 + R_A^2) - \zeta_\beta(r^2 + R_B^2)) \\
&\times r^{l_1^{(\alpha)}} r^{l_1^{(\beta)}} i_{l^{(\alpha)}}(2\zeta_\alpha r R_A) i_{l^{(\beta)}}(2\zeta_\beta r R_B) \\
&\times Y_{l_r^{(\alpha\beta)} m_r^{(\alpha\beta)}}(\Omega) Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\alpha)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_A}) Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\beta)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_B}) \\
&\times \hat{R} \\
&\times C_{\gamma,\delta} \exp(-\zeta_\gamma(r^2 + R_C^2) - \zeta_\delta(r^2 + R_D^2)) \\
&\times r^{l_1^{(\gamma)}} r^{l_1^{(\delta)}} i_{l^{(\gamma)}}(2\zeta_\gamma r R_C) i_{l^{(\delta)}}(2\zeta_\delta r R_D) \\
&\times R_A^{l_2^{(\alpha)}} R_B^{l_2^{(\beta)}} R_C^{l_2^{(\gamma)}} R_D^{l_2^{(\delta)}} \\
&\times Y_{l_r^{(\gamma\delta)} m_r^{(\gamma\delta)}}(\Omega) Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_C}) Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\delta)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\delta)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_D}) d\mathbf{r}
\end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

Sketching the outline of the following steps:

We have to apply $\hat{R}$ to the spherical harmonics dependent on the nucleic polar coordinates, which will yield a sum over a Wigner-D matrix and a new spherical harmonic, e.g.

$$\hat{R} Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_C}) = \sum_{m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)'} = -l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)}}^{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)}} D_{m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)'}}^{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)}} Y_{l_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)} m_{\mathbf{R}}^{(\gamma)'}}(\Omega_{\mathbf{R}_C}) \tag{33}$$

The integral has to be split into a radial and spherical part. The spherical part is over the spherical harmonics dependent on Ω and will yield $\delta_{l_r^{(\alpha\beta)} l_r^{(\gamma\delta)}} \delta_{m_r^{(\alpha\beta)} m_r^{(\gamma\delta)}}$, so we can set $l_r^{(\alpha\beta)} \leftarrow l_r^{(\gamma\delta)}$ as well as $m_r^{(\alpha\beta)} \leftarrow m_r^{(\gamma\delta)}$. The radial part will look like this:

$$\int_{r=0}^{\infty} dr r^2 r^{l_1^{(\alpha)} + l_1^{(\beta)} + l_1^{(\gamma)} + l_1^{(\delta)}} \exp(-(\zeta_\alpha + \zeta_\beta + \zeta_\gamma + \zeta_\delta) r^2) i_{l^{(\alpha)}} i_{l^{(\beta)}} i_{l^{(\gamma)}} i_{l^{(\delta)}} \tag{34}$$

for which we sketch a solution in the next section.

2.2.5 Sketch of Fabrikant-like integration

We now consider the radial integral which contains a product of four modified spherical Bessel functions of the first kind, a power, and an exponential. Our modified spherical Bessel functions of the first kind, i , can be related to the Bessel function of the first kind by relating it to the modified Bessel function of the first kind, $i_n(x) = \sqrt{\pi/(2x)}I_{n+1/2}(x)$, which in turn can be related to the Bessel function of the first kind, $I_n(x) = i^{-n}J_n(ix)$. To follow Fabrikant, we transform those into spherical Bessel functions as $j_n(z) = \sqrt{\pi/(2z)}J_{n+1/2}(z)$.

Formally, our integral looks like

$$I(p, q, i, j, k, l; a, b, c, d) := \int_0^\infty dt \exp(-pt^2) t^q j_i(at) j_j(bt) j_k(ct) j_l(dt) \quad (35)$$

with $p = \zeta_\alpha + \zeta_\beta + \zeta_\gamma + \zeta_\delta$, $q = l_1^{(\alpha)} + l_2^{(\beta)} + l_3^{(\gamma)} + l_4^{(\delta)}$, $t = r$, $a = 2\zeta_\alpha R_A$ and similarly for b, c, d , and $i = l^{(\alpha)}$ and similarly for j, k, l . This can be expanded in terms of zeroth-order spherical Bessel functions,

$$j_0(z) = \text{sinc}(z) \quad (36)$$

where $\text{sinc}(z) = \sin(z)/z$, as

$$j_n(z) := (-1)^n z^n \frac{d^n \text{sinc}(z)}{(z dz)^n} = (-1)^n z^n \left(\frac{d}{z dz} \right)^n \frac{\sin z}{z} \quad (37)$$

and with an argument it is just

$$j_n(at) = (-1)^n (at)^n \left(\frac{d}{at d(at)} \right)^n \frac{\sin(at)}{at} \quad (38)$$

The argument, at , of the differential inside the operator, $d(at)$, can be thought of as $u(a, t) = at$. We can find a suitable expression by rearranging

$$\frac{du}{da} = t \Leftrightarrow du = da t \Leftrightarrow \frac{d}{du} = \frac{1}{t} \frac{d}{da} \quad (39)$$

hence

$$\begin{aligned} j_n(at) &= (-1)^n (at)^n \left(\frac{d}{at t da} \right)^n \frac{\sin(at)}{at} \\ &= (-1)^n a^n \left(\frac{d}{a da} \right)^n \frac{\sin(at)}{at^{1+n}} \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

where in the second line, we cancelled t^n in the left of the operator and one in the denominator of the operator and pulled the other $1/t$ inside the operator into the sinc function on the the right, yielding the factor $1/t^{1+n}$. Substituting this expression four times into the integral in Eq. (35) yields

$$I(p, q, i, j, k, l; a, b, c, d) = (-1)^{i+j+k+l} a^i b^j c^k d^l \frac{\partial^i}{(a\partial a)^i} \frac{\partial^j}{(b\partial b)^j} \frac{\partial^k}{(c\partial c)^k} \frac{\partial^l}{(d\partial d)^l} \left[\int_0^\infty dt \exp(-pt^2) \frac{\sin(at) \sin(bt) \sin(ct) \sin(dt)}{abcd t^{i+j+k+l+3-q}} \right]. \quad (41)$$

This expression where we converted the Bessel functions into trigonometric functions is considerably easier to integrate, since

$$\begin{aligned} \sin(ax) \sin(bx) \sin(cx) \sin(dx) &= 1/8(\cos[(a+b+c+d)x] + \cos[(a+b-c-d)x] \\ &\quad + \cos[(a-b+c-d)x] + \cos[(a-b-c+d)x] \\ &\quad - \cos[(-a+b+c+d)x] - \cos[(a-b+c+d)x] \\ &\quad - \cos[(a+b-c+d)x] - \cos[(a+b+c-d)x]). \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

This yields a sum of a trigonometric function, a power, and an exponential, which can be split into a sum of integrals, I_{part} . This integral is known from the trusty Gradshteyn and Ryzhik (3.952.8)⁷ (GR), where we set the power as $n = -(i+j+k+l+3-q)$, the exponent p remains the same, and a general argument for the cosines, s ,

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\text{part}}(p, s; n) &= \int_0^\infty dt t^n \exp(-pt^2) \cos(st) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} p^{-\frac{n+1}{2}} \exp\left(\frac{-s^2}{4p}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right) {}_1F_1\left(-\frac{n}{2}; \frac{1}{2}; \frac{s^2}{4p}\right) \\ &\stackrel{\text{M}}{=} \frac{1}{2} p^{-\frac{n+1}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right) {}_1F_1\left(-\frac{n+1}{2}; \frac{1}{2}; -\frac{s^2}{4p}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

where the real part of n must be larger than -1 . The last line was computed with Mathematica. A special case with the same caveat is when s is zero, which is, as per GR,

$$I_{\text{part}}(p, 0; n) := \int_0^\infty dt t^n \exp(-pt^2) = \frac{1}{2} p^{-\frac{n+1}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right) \quad (44)$$

which does not occur in our example.

With these results, the integral in Eq. (34) can be solved which yields the overlap, as desired. Too much computational overhead is needed to calculate the nested sum though. The most straightforward remedy is the approximation of all functions with s -functions, as done in the main article and detailed in the section above. Another way to simplify the preceding procedure is outlined in the following section.

2.3 Exclude higher-order function interactions

Instead of calculating all higher-order interactions of functions in Eq. (51) in the main article, we restrict the calculation to either any interaction if the two electrons to be compared are on the same atom, or, if it is two-centered, only the pairs of an s -function with any other higher-order function are included, hence excluding the combinations of two p -functions or a d -function and a p -function. Reducing the number of functions like this, reduces the complexity of the density overlap and makes it more feasible to calculate.

We tested the difference between a regular density, containing all higher-order pair terms, and a density where they are excluded (Figure 5).

According to Eq. (51), we then obtain

$$\rho_{\text{el}}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{A,B}^M \sum_{\substack{\alpha \textcircled{A} \\ \beta \textcircled{B}}} \begin{cases} [L_\alpha = 0 \vee L_\beta = 0] D_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha \chi_\beta & \text{for } \alpha \neq \beta \\ D_{\alpha\beta} \chi_\alpha \chi_\beta & \text{for } \alpha = \beta \end{cases} \quad (45)$$

where the Iverson brackets are $[P] = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } P \text{ is true} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

and denote that either of the two centers must be an s -function.

We tested this approximation qualitatively by plotting the full density with STO-3G⁸ with Gaussian⁹ and visualized it with Avogadro¹⁰ in SI Figure 5. In a customized version of Avogadro, we set to zero all pairwise coefficients of higher order (b). Without any interaction at all and retaining only the diagonal of the coefficient matrix, we obtain c). The difference between the full density and the one without higher order terms can be seen in d), which turns out to be a qualitatively well justified approximation, while the difference between the full density and the diagonal only, shown in e), highlights larger deviations.

The derivation for a mathematical treatment is very similar to the one outlined for the exact SOED above except that some of the terms cancel or simplify.

(a) Full density.

(b) Density without multi-center higher order orbitals.

(c) Density only without multi-center orbitals.

(d) Density difference between the full density and the one without multi-center higher order orbitals.

(e) Density difference between the full density and the one without higher order orbitals.

Figure 5: In (a), the full density is shown. In the molecular coefficient matrix, we can neglect all coefficients that refer to pairs of higher order functions, i.e. p - p interaction, p - d and d - p interaction, as well as d - d interaction, when they are on different nuclei (i.e. on the off-diagonal). This leads to a density shown in (b). If we neglect all off-diagonal coefficients, we arrive at (c). The latter is not necessary, since the difficulties originate from the higher order function at different centers. If they are on the same center, it does not lead to complications. In (d), we show the difference between the full density and (b), and in (e) we show the difference between the full density and (c), which is a much coarser approximation and leads to positive pockets (in red).

3 Our SOAP Module

All SOAP and SOED calculations were carried out with a new implementation of Eq. (40) in the main paper, which avoids the power series expansion of in standard applications of SOAP.⁶

4 Cartesian Coordinates of all Molecules in Angstrom

4.1 Reaction 1

14			
reactant			
C	-1.8843720675	0.1118253877	0.7752642205
C	0.6949809787	-0.9746341777	0.0247783307
O	-0.1047505509	-1.7898023304	0.5965789546
N	1.8005378734	-1.1143218545	-0.6553266430
C	-1.0357023940	0.6974485864	-0.1560342820
C	0.3929464278	0.6583726786	0.0861340669
N	1.3656179385	1.1925705852	-0.8141970780
C	2.1131547882	0.1709658586	-1.1232388473
H	-1.0339069469	-1.1513055530	0.7101278330
H	-2.9474027972	-0.0389253512	0.5263903688
H	-1.6640427516	0.2293072663	1.8543660110
H	-1.3595587791	0.8520931961	-1.2014601059
H	0.6627268526	0.8754830560	1.1482497174
H	2.9997714281	0.2809226518	-1.7716325468
14			
ts			
C	-2.0212197833	0.3649065065	0.7624689009
C	0.7762326251	-0.9537862747	0.0236576061
O	0.0765223497	-1.9195581935	0.6027179293
N	1.8564067983	-1.1193144595	-0.6774647872
C	-1.0960564597	0.6642774410	-0.1750909141
C	0.3743798327	0.5276914068	0.0906753346
N	1.3310512967	1.1642323596	-0.8020052665
C	2.1263427661	0.1894628541	-1.1369349453
H	-0.8006482486	-1.5289653436	0.8402913307
H	-3.0955724214	0.3280754503	0.5264159011
H	-1.7375355785	0.1912725740	1.8165936841
H	-1.3911560724	0.8743172747	-1.2170844069
H	0.5954486856	0.8706080015	1.1306838144
H	3.0058042096	0.3467804026	-1.7849241811

14

product			
C	-1.9390084795	0.1216112969	0.8173939329
C	1.0363728189	-1.6424291956	-0.0931516258
O	0.3300577563	-2.3778426396	0.5004660595
N	1.9137924101	-1.0866841591	-0.7667679667
C	-0.9061423148	0.5715711852	-0.1669488688
C	0.3420483658	0.9784629616	0.1696482009
N	1.3768682942	1.2440262436	-0.7330572821
C	2.0875888846	0.2517565025	-1.1332485196
H	-1.9960646540	-0.9913182993	0.8132639674
H	-2.9545140972	0.4939450604	0.5718576673
H	-1.6904611505	0.4305657512	1.8524881097
H	-1.1474906724	0.4867809944	-1.2423444512
H	0.6152889515	1.1045181159	1.2372284405
H	2.9316638872	0.4150361819	-1.8268276640

4.2 Reaction 2

20			
reactant			
C	-1.5871877940	0.4085709190	0.9185292247
C	0.6799499068	-0.9379160394	-0.3113873230
O	0.1940997452	-1.4914317843	0.7420567815
N	1.5209387024	-1.3694178578	-1.2197335174
C	-1.2540408231	0.4851196815	-0.4238190111
C	0.1731045683	0.5277596355	-0.7580912957
N	0.6691373228	0.6478917316	-2.1024820933
C	1.4302115951	-0.3952098837	-2.2052962273
H	-0.7341791382	-0.8378472735	0.8527780068
H	-2.6228554287	0.1568204398	1.2306614159
H	-0.4655227327	-0.3569669191	3.3151366953
H	-1.9692119826	0.1188524759	-1.1773435332
H	0.7232992970	1.2234544979	-0.0796161729
O	1.7065321892	-0.4681056720	-4.5055774999
N	2.2655269018	-0.5838326737	-3.4227414345
O	3.4503868487	-0.8244339749	-3.2167567161
O	-0.8353674579	1.0936306005	1.8422866476
C	-0.9392626968	0.6405949561	3.1889491989
H	-0.4037969398	1.3768597270	3.8155604286
H	-2.0017620836	0.5856074136	3.5168864250

20

ts

C	-1.7039457237	0.6472293157	0.8906050760
C	0.7601683881	-0.9658410957	-0.3549822706
O	0.4414467669	-1.6425662128	0.7364452440
N	1.5856585386	-1.3829948799	-1.2701966178
C	-1.3124714874	0.4362443846	-0.3912305795
C	0.1546997624	0.3960237862	-0.7172839829
N	0.6254619133	0.6062128851	-2.0815332927
C	1.4344788930	-0.3916015971	-2.2395262145
H	-0.3815230140	-1.2269765761	1.0855233501
H	-2.7573638723	0.5625979079	1.2218250207
H	-0.5820985527	-0.3693713442	3.3435378488
H	-2.0515822538	0.1724212000	-1.1604831553
H	0.6727164831	1.1434331616	-0.0669227147
O	1.6986206557	-0.4247565633	-4.5443951497
N	2.2638540916	-0.5358759470	-3.4642745436
O	3.4543045219	-0.7577226109	-3.2651002854
O	-0.8015512068	1.0603907592	1.8261476087
C	-0.9937138233	0.6521381016	3.1742453342
H	-0.4392167342	1.3621926212	3.8153651361
H	-2.0679433464	0.6588227039	3.4622341881

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product

C	-1.6605719822	0.3475370056	0.9228626248
C	1.0430010013	-1.5308973075	-0.1694388020
O	0.6558512260	-1.9231543267	0.8704216568
N	1.6111044350	-1.3415238616	-1.2569968482
C	-1.1707962133	0.3922783236	-0.4930691713
C	0.0486276197	0.8723824581	-0.8275381885
N	0.6677606580	0.7047206532	-2.0748011985
C	1.4027968891	-0.3318026200	-2.1739499355
H	-1.7114081563	-0.7376755255	1.2063559564
H	-2.7118310308	0.7285425839	1.0015531222
H	-0.4865540030	-0.4107137917	3.2672303075
H	-1.8044155391	-0.0926016285	-1.2547128247
H	0.6577968995	1.3794061396	-0.0543978674
O	1.6687308516	-0.3995721095	-4.4952078462
N	2.2322882592	-0.5259462887	-3.4200355988
O	3.4144473109	-0.7790061158	-3.2160845217
O	-0.7938904088	1.0441391238	1.7838446006
C	-0.8776309346	0.6261209077	3.1303096685
H	-0.2618348577	1.3201289402	3.7342297908
H	-1.9234720245	0.6576374399	3.5194250751

4.3 Reaction 3

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reactant

C	-2.2093812622	0.3745445801	1.0869787823
C	0.1318205933	-0.8466480183	-0.2161082950
O	-0.4972146095	-1.5949917006	0.6367444717
N	1.0041882432	-1.1304334783	-1.1389504362
C	-1.6334577315	0.7704521843	-0.1040470967
C	-0.1758156099	0.7199794856	-0.2787370831
N	0.4839933350	1.1340016110	-1.4853826471
C	1.1569447661	0.0786747198	-1.8655662036
H	-1.3443231640	-0.9761981024	0.8567232688
H	-3.2995421729	0.1846771648	1.0595928911
H	-3.1183840843	-0.6122217671	3.5663531590
H	-2.2342939336	0.7649342264	-1.0308194698
H	0.3689259937	1.1314726779	0.6046898025
H	3.9670644341	0.4427323687	-1.9944669101
C	-1.6691869211	0.6366639773	2.4906948403
H	-2.1090289564	1.6078900638	2.8137244200
H	-0.5710813678	0.7933713523	2.4710347393
C	-2.0228455722	-0.4427002449	3.5179765601
H	-1.5413244582	-1.4095831486	3.2680666473
H	-1.6845137115	-0.1525549519	4.5323167597
C	2.0768081722	0.0745097718	-3.0498296078
H	2.0252216984	1.0744010389	-3.5226543930
H	1.6822827048	-0.6656621446	-3.7808627956
C	3.5180629309	-0.3045208337	-2.6804082255
H	3.5397398478	-1.2888914769	-2.1721677594
H	4.1553408359	-0.3638993555	-3.5848954192

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ts

C	-2.3231208358	0.6342452564	1.1155334315
C	0.2081656285	-0.8874405740	-0.2275837095
O	-0.2994199536	-1.7646378982	0.6332261799
N	1.0553097609	-1.1630238884	-1.1661715695
C	-1.6881653897	0.6973991987	-0.0831700053
C	-0.1983459225	0.5897317617	-0.2499135080
N	0.4460058019	1.0808489830	-1.4596288537
C	1.1600502708	0.0681952045	-1.8751810491
H	-1.1134853325	-1.3453987177	1.0037472078
H	-3.4275046203	0.5773665947	1.0979253500
H	-3.1381371572	-0.6050830765	3.5177875642
H	-2.2783065996	0.6742993091	-1.0146526003
H	0.3130676598	1.0765992213	0.6150964381
H	3.9731808255	0.4617714754	-2.0038037715
C	-1.7104562754	0.7285523243	2.4941107240
H	-2.0893608046	1.6714201746	2.9499596256
H	-0.6088307375	0.8495787995	2.4320644351
C	-2.0449489403	-0.4290992993	3.4512000256
H	-1.5682221661	-1.3818199101	3.1392327695
H	-1.6798036870	-0.2070229351	4.4739597656
C	2.0798063290	0.1000780368	-3.0587150619
H	2.0243340059	1.1048744345	-3.5203307195
H	1.6904482865	-0.6335065297	-3.7994906474
C	3.5211993916	-0.2833150196	-2.6901233376
H	3.5375273600	-1.2675712002	-2.1812201578
H	4.1590131017	-0.3470417258	-3.5938585257

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product

C	-2.2640854880	0.2934275818	1.0782094707
C	0.3934605020	-1.5133236643	-0.2129616138
O	-0.1385691088	-2.1089502035	0.6589078148
N	1.0844336605	-1.1257026633	-1.1619607725
C	-1.5347767539	0.7145860782	-0.1692348270
C	-0.2264308167	1.0602097626	-0.2541552790
N	0.5102993055	1.1663462952	-1.4386521697
C	1.1498743879	0.1165994538	-1.8300378345
H	-2.3491295423	-0.8183138781	0.9977250969
H	-3.3167994456	0.6506945919	1.0450381265
H	-3.1108449727	-0.5331644985	3.6062483457
H	-2.0838220178	0.5826922882	-1.1196452892
H	0.3681591920	1.2312828851	0.6647915838
H	3.9579925586	0.4870475602	-1.9974736634
C	-1.6391068434	0.6210931996	2.4443454137
H	-1.9421349378	1.6442497644	2.7547970293
H	-0.5317589407	0.6488315644	2.3637615573
C	-2.0118142867	-0.4015406613	3.5225199761
H	-1.5765003156	-1.3937816344	3.2821467034
H	-1.6336887984	-0.1024871883	4.5209186518
C	2.0567250792	0.1109238108	-3.0322438437
H	1.9942617741	1.1121234614	-3.4991937182
H	1.6551035507	-0.6291390958	-3.7593408846
C	3.5063833972	-0.2591285542	-2.6824430102
H	3.5523522386	-1.2488814872	-2.1856185852
H	4.1304166224	-0.3056947686	-3.5964482790

5 Integration over Euler angles

To give a visual understanding of the integration over $SO(3)$, see Figure 6.

Figure 6: A visualization to give an intuitive understanding of the integration over three orthogonal axes: The superposition between the reactant and the transition state of Reaction 1 is shown in the first panel. In the following three panels, the transition state is rotated around three orthogonal axes. These axis could for instance be the Euler angles. To avoid “double counting” when integrating, the integration measure (Haar measure) is needed, as explained in the main article.

6 RMSD-based overlap kernel

To achieve translational invariance, all molecules are centered on the origin of the coordinate system with their center of mass. In the procedure to obtain the SOAP kernel,⁶ one of the two molecules is integrated over all possible rotations to gain rotational invariance. A natural simplification of this would be to only use the maximum overlap. Yet, to find the maximum, all possible rotations would need to be considered. Instead of minimizing the overlap which is a costly operation, an efficient alternative might be minimizing the root-mean-square deviation, $\text{RMSD} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_i^2}$, where δ_i is the distance between two atoms i in both molecules. This procedure finds the best aligned orientations of the two molecular structures and may serve as a proxy for the maximum overlap. But even though a similarity matrix can be built, it would not be a valid kernel, as it is not positive semidefinite. The kernel would be defined as

$$K(x, U_{x,x'}x') = x \cdot U_{x,x'}x' \quad (46)$$

where $U_{x,x'}$ is the rotation matrix that brings coordinates x' to an overlap with coordinates x , i.e. minimizing the RMSD between the two structures.

The issue arises that one molecule, A , can be in an arbitrary orientation (see Figure 7). The second, B , will be oriented according to the first to minimize the RMSD, $B' = U_{AB}B$. This new orientation for B , namely B' , needs to be adapted for all subsequent comparisons. Similarly, we will obtain $C' = U_{AC}C$. Comparing molecules B and C will lead to a conflict because they are already relative to A (marked with a star). The consistent way would be to compare the RMSD of B' and C' such that one molecule is always in the same orientation.

Figure 7: The molecules A , B , and C on top and on the right are compared via RMSD in a pairwise fashion. On the diagonal, the RMSD is always 0 as the overlap is perfect. Comparing a fixed A with B will re-orient B as $B' = U_{AB} B$ (second cell) and minimize the RMSD. Similarly for the comparison between a fixed A and C (third cell). The issue arises (third cell in second row) when the already (with respect to A) oriented B , namely B' , is compared with C' , which is C oriented with respect to A . We can either leave them in their determined, A -dependent orientations which will not minimize the RMSD but leave the features consistent or re-orient one of them to minimize the RMSD, which results in the matrix not comparing the same structures over all pairwise comparisons.

However, this would not produce a minimum RMSD. The RMSD-minimizing comparison would be either $B'' = U_{CB} C$ or $C''' = U_{BC} C$ but then we use multiple rotations for one molecule. From this analysis we see that RMSD cannot be straightforwardly used with molecular structures as they would need to be brought into a rotation invariant form beforehand.

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